

DETECTIVE STORIES by E.A. BY: FEATURES OF GENRE AND COMPOSITION

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the analysis of detective stories by the famous American writer Edgar Allan Poe. The main attention is paid to identifying the features of the genre and composition that make Poe's works unique in the context of detective literature. Through a detailed study of the structural elements and stylistic techniques, the author of the article sets himself the task of revealing the internal logic and characteristic features of the detective works of E.A. Poe.

Key words: Edgar Allan Poe, detective stories, features of the genre, composition, structure of works, literary analysis, stylistic devices, narrative logic, American literature, detective classics.

Edgar Allan Poe is generally recognized as the founder of the detective genre in American literature. His works are full of mysteries and secrets, making the atmosphere of his short stories fascinating and even frightening. From the first lines, the reader is immersed in the plot, sees a mystery in it and strives to unravel it. The uniqueness and unique charm of the works of E.A. Poe also attaches his commitment to "rationalistic romanticism." There are a number of features in the prose of Edgar Allan Poe that allow us to talk about the specifics of the detective genre he developed.

Russian literary scholars, for example Rudnev [8], O.V. Fedunin consider detective prose as a product of mass culture [9]. And this inevitably leads to stereotyping in plots and imagery, "a rejection of metaphysical seriousness and a craving for the unmotivated" [8, p. 114]. Such a unification of the detective genre seems irrational in relation to its discoverer. In our work, we focus on the genre and architectural features of the "scary" short stories of the American prose writer.

Let us turn, firstly, to the architectonics of the stories of the creator of The Golden Bug. When first acquainted with his prose, the reader notices the small size of E.A.'s short stories. By. This feature allows you to read them immediately without interruption. In this way, the reader can be completely immersed in the plot and experience all the subtleties of the plot that the author is trying to convey to him. After all, Edgar Allan Poe believed that every sentence must be

thought out and must relate to the main idea of the plot. From the very beginning, the author already knows what result he wants to reach by the end of the short story, so his short stories often have a ring composition. Often E. A. Poe begins his stories with justifications or explanations and then tells the main story. This architecture of stories allows the author to capture the reader's attention from the very beginning of the story and arouse curiosity about the outcome of the story. This compositional structure gives his works integrity, in which the end of the story closes on its beginning.

In addition to the integrity of the text, E.A. Poe also adheres to emotional unity. In his short stories, he creates a special mood, so gloomy and cold. In addition, he manages to maintain this mood throughout the entire narrative, thereby constantly keeping the reader in suspense. This helps increase the suspense, and the reader's desire to solve the mystery only increases. The reader begins to feel like an invisible hero of the story, as if he himself is standing next to the heroes and observing. An example of creating tension is the novella "The Tell-Tale Heart," in which every night, at the stroke of midnight, the killer watched his victim. He did this with extreme caution in order to remain unnoticed, "... I opened the lantern with caution - with great caution - I opened it (after all, the hinges could creak) ..." [7, p.444], "... I opened the door with extreme caution. My hand slid slower than the minute hand on a clock" [7, p.444]. Such a description of the hero's actions conveys to the reader the special tension that the hero himself experiences. The reader begins to feel as if time is dragging on endlessly, which makes him even more interested and makes him look forward to the outcome.

E.A. Poe was the first writer in American literature to use real crime stories in his short stories. Some of his stories are actually based on crime articles from newspapers, for example, "The Mystery of Marie Roget." In such short stories, the author implements a special type of "mystery-investigation" story. At the very beginning of the novel, E. Poe creates a mystery; it can be either a mysterious murder or a map with encrypted instructions. Then the main character conducts an investigation, studying in detail all the details of the case, while the author describes in detail the hero's reasoning. And at the end of the story, the detective hero superbly manages to solve the riddle, and he gives a detailed explanation of the entire crime. Based on this method, E. A. Poe wrote a trilogy, which included short stories: "Murder in the Rue Morgue," "The Purloined Letter," and "The Mystery of Marie Roget." In these stories, the main character is the aristocrat Auguste Dupin. He has amazing analytical skills and

plays the role of a hero analyst while solving crimes. Thus, the reader has the opportunity, through the image of Auguste Dupin, to imagine himself as a detective who is conducting an investigation, revealing other people's secrets and details of horrific crimes. The same rigor and desire for rationalism can be seen in these short stories. "Murder in the Rue Morgue" begins with the author's discussions about analytics, its features and advantages. Even the methods of the police cannot compare with the analytical method of Auguste Dupin. He himself calls the police investigation "a parody of the investigation" [7, p. 316]. The hero takes up the case not in an effort to help the police find the criminal, but for entertainment purposes, saying: "Such an investigation will amuse us..." [7, p.317]. For Auguste Dupin, this investigation represents a kind of competition with the police. At the end of the story, when the hero manages to solve the crime, while the police went on the wrong trail, Auguste Dupin says with satisfaction: "It's enough for me that I beat the enemy on his territory" [7, p. 334]. Auguste Dupin's method consists of the ability to observe, notice small details that at first glance seem insignificant, as well as the ability to put oneself in the place of another person and assess the situation from his point of view. It is this method of analytical investigation that E. Poe describes in his detective stories.

Another interesting feature of E. Poe's short stories is that they are all written in the first person, and all these characters are very similar to the writer himself. And in the lines of the short story "William Wilson," E. Poe addresses the reader: "Let me call myself William Wilson this time" [7, p. 273], which once again proves his personal presence in the works. You can also feel this through the characters of his characters. For example, the main characters of the short stories "The Black Cat" and "The Tell-Tale Heart" are people with an unhealthy psyche, due to illness or alcoholism. It is worth recalling that the life of the writer himself was not easy, he also suffered from alcoholism, and after the death of his wife, his condition worsened, he completely lost himself.

When comparing Auguste Dupin and William Legrand, it is necessary to note their talent for analytics. While Auguste Dupin successfully solves crimes that seem incredibly complex, William Legrand brilliantly copes with a tricky task, the solution of which leads him to the sought-after treasure. E. Poe's heroes, as true representatives of the detective genre, have an analytical mind, a penchant for rationalism, the ability to logic, non-standard thinking, that is, all the necessary set of properties of a real detective, capable of unraveling the bizarre intricacies of criminals.

Another interesting feature of E. A. Poe's manner is that he paid special attention to the internal state of his heroes. So, for example, in the short story "Murder in the Rue Morgue" the author does not give an external description of Auguste Dupin. All we know about him is a little history of his family. At the same time, Edgar Allan Poe describes in detail the internal state of the hero, which is very similar to the state of the narrator. They withdrew from society, did not leave the house for months, and their friends did not know their whereabouts. Both of them preferred the darkness of the night, which is why they closed the shutters tightly during the day, and went out into the street only after sunset, walking until late at night. On the one hand, Auguste Dupin is secretive and prefers to spend time alone, reading books or studying newspaper articles, but on the other hand, with what enthusiasm he takes on the investigation, how lively and, at times, unconventionally, he manages to expose secrets. With the help of such a description, the reader can fully understand the nature of the hero and, perhaps, find similarities with himself.

The identified features allow us to distinguish two types of detective stories in Edgar Poe's short stories. In one case, there is no detective character in the story; the author assigns this role to the reader. For example, in such short stories as "The Black Cat" and "The Tell-Tale Heart" E. Poe describes the commission of a crime, but does not give a hero who would investigate it. In this case, the reader observes the actions of the characters throughout the story and can make their own assumptions about the outcome.

In the short stories of the second type there is a character - a detective who conducts his own investigation, describing very complex analytical connections. Examples of such short stories are the stories included in the trilogy about the analyst Auguste Dupin. Studying the descriptions of crimes, the reader comes to the conclusion that it is hardly possible to solve these cases. But Auguste Dupin's voluminous and detailed conclusions amaze the reader with their complexity and logic. With these arguments, E. A. Poe once again proves that the short story must have integrity, while every detail of the investigation is taken into account. This type of detective subsequently becomes a classic.

Thus, in accordance with the genre matrix of a detective work, all components of the detective model appear in Edgar Allan Poe's short stories: the hero-detective, the criminal as his antagonist, personal motives for the crime, "the rational-game method of investigating an exceptional and strange crime," "the relationship of the hero with the world of the author-reader" [9, p. 62-63]. The writer managed to masterfully create the atmosphere of the story, come up with

magnificent plots that had not yet been found in the literature of the 19th century and were innovations. Each short story written by E. A. Poe exists as a whole organism, in it everything from the capacious title, the intricacies of the plot, and to the unexpected denouement merges together. His characters are unique and similar at the same time. The author manages to be invisibly present in each of his short stories, masterfully transforming himself into “the author-commentator of current events” [2, p.5].

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